

The complicated adverse effect relating to the used of direct herbal traditional extract(medicine) arbitrary in reciprocal to the use of modified herbal syrup containing antioxidants/nutraceuticals supplements (polyherbal drugs/syrup) as an active antiaging therapy for the clinicals and challenges in monitoring

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Abstract

Genetic(Pathogenic microbial free radical), lifestyle (social engagement) and environmental(free radical) are becoming unfathomable nowadays. Thus the rapid socio-economical development in recent decades, the proportion of elderly has rapidly, geometrically and arithmetically increased worldwide. In addition, many aging -related diseases have shown an upward trend, including nervous system disease, cardiovascular diseases, metabolic diseases, cancer diseases, covid-19 viral suppression infections, HIV/AIDS viral suppression infections etc., respectively. The burden of aging related disease has become an urgent global health wise challenge; thus, which would have been tackle with immediate alacrity for permanent solution. Although therapies involving these agents have shown promising potential with the efficacy of a good number of herbal products clearly established, many of them remain untested and their use are either poorly monitored or not even monitored at all. The consequence of this is an inadequate knowledge of their mode of action, potential adverse reactions, contraindications, and interactions with existing orthodox pharmaceuticals and functional foods to promote both safe and rational use of these agents. Since safety continues to be a major issue with the use of herbal remedies, it becomes imperative, therefore, that relevant regulatory authorities put in place appropriate measures to protect public. Selected ingredients of these dietary supplements include several vitamins, mineral, phytochemicals, complex of amino acid residues(proteins), probiotics, vitamins A, B, C, D and E assist in maintaining skin veracity. Zinc, Copper, and Selenium are the main minerals which are involve in sustenance of healthy skin. Phytochemical consisting of flavonoid, terpenoid, and alkaloids with antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidative property may benefit the texture and physiological parameters of skin delay.. In view of his review, it talks about results, discussions,toxicity-related issues and major safety concerns arising from the use of herbal medicinal products and also highlights some important challenges associated with effective monitoring of their bio-safety

Keywords: Aging; Supplements; Natural Products; Pathogenic Free Radical/Free Radical; Microorganisms; Bioactive Compounds; Phytochemical; Antioxidants

1. Introduction

The unprecedented and accommodation of herbal medicine along side with phytonutrient or nutraceuticals have rapidly and tremendously created a profound impact through traditional herbal medicine for the consciousness of therapeutic obligation through healthcare. Thus, many people who were initially getting lost of the entire issues through

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the intake of traditional herbal treatment as per those days; are now currently resorting their interest by getting themselves so acclimatized with the traditional herbal products for treatment of various health challenges in different local, national and global (WHO) [1]. Obviously in the past decade some doubting Thomas witnessed a tremendous surge in acceptance and public interest in natural therapies both in developing and developed countries for effective usage. To these effect the herbal remedies being made available not only in drug storage, but it also now in syrup storage in readiness for marketing. Furthermore is has been so assiduously and painstakingly estimated of the truth that up to four billion people (representing 80% of the world's population) living in the developing world rely on herbal medicinal products as a primary source of healthcare and traditional medical practice which involves the use of herbs is viewed as an integral part of the culture in those communities [2]

Taking a consensus study of those who might have had doubting Thomas by fear of taking traditional herbal medicine which is by now more certain of the fact that people should not have been casting doubt for their biosafety. Thus. it is always very important the processes through which the local herbal medicine starting from the raw material to the finishing would rather have met the international regulatory (WHO) Standard. Even though we've not specified at what age group would this have an impact in one longevity or delay age. In 2010, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that, 8% (524 million) of the world's 1 population was aged 65 years and above. For this reason, it is has been estimated that by 2050, this age group will make up 116% (1.5 billion) of the world's population. The result of this increased longevity is an increasing interest in how to slow down aging. This interest in anti-aging is compounded by the increasingly cosmetic world that we live in. The question now is, can we really slow down aging? Currently, there are a lot of studies in which skin aging is reported as the goal or target for biomedical and scientific [3] interventions using nutrition. How do we age? Two independent, clinical and biological mechanisms (intrinsic and extrinsic) are responsible for skin aging. These two mechanisms combine to cause phenotypic changes in skin cells. They also cause structural and functional changes in extracellular matrix components such as collagen, elastin and proteoglycans which provide tensile strength,[4] elasticity, and hydration to the skin. The intrinsic mechanism represents chronological aging and it is inevitable. Intrinsic aging results from a decline of biological functions and the action of reactive oxygen species (ROS) following cellular metabolism. Factors which contribute to this mechanism of aging include; cellular metabolism, [5]

In view of our study, It has become so essential, therefore, to furnish the general public including healthcare professionals with adequate information to facilitate better understanding of the risks associated with the use of these products and to ensure that all medicines are safe and of suitable quality. Results and Discussions in this review is more or less limited to toxicity-related issues and major safety concerns arising from the use of herbal medicines as well as factors promoting them. Some important challenges associated with effective monitoring of safety of these herbal remedies are also highlighted with a view to helping refocus relevant regulatory agencies on the need for effectiveness and ensuring adequate protection of public health and promoting biosafety through the use of divine polyherbal chocolate medicine syrup.

1.1. Statement of research problem

The recent growth in the knowledge of free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in biology is producing a medical revolution that promises a new age of health and disease management. [6] It is ironic that oxygen, an element indispensable for life, [7] under certain situations has deleterious effects on the human body. [8] Most of the potentially harmful effects of oxygen are due to the formation and activity of a number of chemical compounds, known as ROS, which have a tendency to donate oxygen to other substances. Free radicals and antioxidants have become commonly used terms in modern discussions of disease mechanisms.[9]

A free radical can be defined as any molecular species capable of independent existence that contains an unpaired electron in an atomic orbital. The presence of an unpaired electron results in certain common properties that are shared by most radicals. Many radicals are unstable and highly reactive. They can either donate an electron to or accept an electron from other molecules, therefore behaving as oxidants or reductants. [10] The most important oxygen-containing free radicals in many disease states are hydroxyl radical, superoxide anion radical, hydrogen peroxide, oxygen singlet, hypochlorite, nitric oxide radical, and peroxynitrite radical. These are highly reactive species, capable in the nucleus, and in the membranes of cells of damaging biologically relevant molecules such as DNA, proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids. [11] Free radicals attack important macromolecules leading to cell damage and homeostatic disruption. Targets of free radicals include all kinds (industrial chemical, radiation, environmental pollution, drugs/drugs abuse, xenobiotics, alcoholic, illegal sex transmission with their causative pathogenic agents (virus, bacteria, fungal, smoking etc., respectively of molecules in the body. Among them, lipids, nucleic acids, and proteins are the major targets.

Psychological mechanisms or activities of lipid/ cholesterol in peoples organs, system, tissue and organelles that always led one in early aging. It's possible for one to live for 120years without needing pills. Why chronic incurable disease are constant companion or clogged vessel:

1.2. Hidden and overt signal dirty vessels

The most wider-spread cause of death on the planet are cardiovascular diseases. The main reason behind their development in older people Cholesterol that a line makes cholesterol the most dangerous substance on the planet. These substances kills people more often than alcohol, nicotine and drug combined. For instant 94% of cases, if a person does not live to 80 years old cholesterol he /she is to be blame. Cholesterol destroys one's body if it wouldn't accumulated in the blood vessels than people could easily live for up to 120years. What is cholesterol and how does it look like? The undisputed workaholic research fellow wouldn't describe the process in detail as one could find all that in medical text books. For example one could imagine cooled fat left over from a frying pan that has not been wash as ruminants and it accumulated form a white ice soft substance in the dinner plate(that is what cholesterol look like). To a lay man understanding, the white ice soften substance when in the blood settle on the walls of blood vessels, first in the form of a smaller layer when one is up to (20-25 years). Thus the cholesterol layer grows rapidly (25-40 years) as more and more particles stick to it. Eventually when one is up to 40 years of old the cholesterol takes up almost half the space in one blood vessels. In response to this the heart has no choice but to increase the pressure(For instant let consider the simple basic principle of Charles's/boy's law in our basic chemistry when pressure increase the volume decrease at constant temperature in vessel. In our good days of youthfulness having bicycle so affectionally, when the tier having gone down flat without air, so using an ordinary pump to justify the air into the flat tier repeatedly by force would invariably reduce the volume in the vessel. For this reason or assuming the pipeline vessel is too small for the air to pass through normally heat always evolve at high pressure. Similar event has also been observe for blood to have passed through thick fat/cholesterol in human vessel for justification. However, it has always been observed for heat(high blood pressure) to evolve at the tail end of an ordinary bicycle pump). A person who has surges and age -related hypertension and all that it entails), but that is not even the most dangerous part. Much more dangerous is the fact that cholesterol could be completely clogs the small vessels that permeate all tissues as a results of deterioration in the blood supply pathological processes develop. In the internal organs because of this chronic diseases start to develop. The stomach is the first to fall, then the spleen and after while the person develops steriosis of the liver and pancreas. Usually in such cases these implies the prompt and complete shut down of the person's blood system(cholesterol is what triggers this process more often). Literally everything in the body depends on the state of the vessels. If the vessels becomes clogged in the legs this would rather led to varicose, vein, constant edema and a feeling of heaviness. if in the liver then hepatitis and cirrhosis occurs, if in the joints then arthritis and arthrosis or pain in the spine, if the

Figure 1 29 worst heart and artery foods that unclog arteries

vessels are clogged in eyes then the person gradually becomes blind all together. Thus one cannot avoid vessels becoming clogged; cholesterol accumulates in the vessels of every person; dirt in the blood vessels is the one of the major causes of rapid aging. it is cholesterol starts the aging chain reaction in the body. And its the pollution of blood vessels that shortens a person's life even though nature intended it to be longer. Wow !! that's great of doctors' findings and what about the illegal sex transmission by illegal causative pathogen viruses (HIV, Covid-19, Papilloma virus, Ebola etc., respectively through human genomic system)? Should that be avoided or not part of syndrome of early aging?

However, instead of one living to 120 years (this is how long ones organs can last) people often die before their natural age design for them to live on this planets earth 70 years! Ocobeh hypertension die at the age of 40-50 years. By the way it is one of the most obvious symptom of vascular contamination, that's is only ones feeding(carbohydrates) aspect of life and what about the virus infections which are prone to be mutagenic and carcinogenic due to illegal sexual intercourse (un notice biological weapon of mass destruction).

Industrial pollution, drug, environmental pollution, alcoholic etc., would be treated as in the case of heavy metals(Chromium, nickel, titanium, etc., respectively could be place under thrombus mass

Thrombus Mass: if cholesterol resembles fat, then thrombus mass (Blood clots) resemble cottage cheese. Thrombus growth form on the inner walls of the blood vessels. The risk of blood clots is even higher than with cholesterol. At any moment the thrombus can detach from the vessels walls and block a smaller vessels in the heart or brain, which will lead to a heart attack or stroke respectively. Both are very often fatal, and if the person somehow survives their body will have taken serious damage. The older a person gets, the higher the risk that blood clot will detach. This is why older people so often die from a stroke or heart attack as shown in fig1 &2

Figure 2 Posted vitamins, mineral, and antioxidant prevent clogged arteries

Heavy metals like those of salts of mercury, chromium, nickel titanium at time zinc ion but not in it atom does not exhibit the character of d- orbital (heavy metal). Various chemicals that a person has accumulated in their body during their life. If a person for example work in a hazardous industry they have the chances of increase deposited of such element in their vital organs. Although given the current ecology, heavy metals build ups accumulate in everyone. These substances have already proven are carcinogenic and mutagenic (weapon of mass destruction). Thus, this has contributed to abnormal cell division which could more or less led to cancer. Almost 98% of those who die from cancer have high level of some crystalline deposits in their blood. We've known that mercury, calcium crystal and chromium in its ionic state (Cr+6) hexavalent are known to be harmful and with a large accumulation of it in the blood its self-become toxic

By the age of 50, a persons blood vessels are clogged throughout the body. The more the polluted vessels, the more the disease is likely to be intensified, the faster one age and the worse one feel. As seen in fig 1.

1.3. Nucleic acid and protein targeted by causative pathogens (virus, bacteria, fungi) through legal sex (ones wife/ wives) / arbitral illegal sex to students and many ladies that could led to ones early aging

Taking a critical view of the virus that has immensely contributed to a global outbreak in 2003 (Silas at el.,2020) once again as in 27th- 28th April 2020 confirm cases was 3,034,603, recovered cases was 892599, death toll 210,842 respectively. In just three weeks or so the findings have risen to about 3.6 million confirm cases, followed by recovery cases with about 1.18 million and the death toll was about 69,000. Thus, what is the hope of humanity to her futuristic endeavor regarding to development. Is it in progress or degeneration? (Silas el at.,2020). Taking a bold step of faith by considering how covid-19 do have access in to the host cell. For this reason and to a layman understanding (simple protein syntheses) as could be view in figure 3. the molecule of mRNA from a double DNA helix shape providing the codes to synthesized a protein. In the process of translation, the mRNA gradually moves in the cytoplasm to attaching itself to ribosome a long side with codon, in the process of time the tRNA molecules became so activated in the cytoplasm once again through which its shuttles alongside with anticodon carrying the appropriate amino acid to the ribosome. One by one coded by sequential triplet codon on the mRNA until a complex protein is finally synthesized or yielded Thus, one might not have come across of alteration in their bases (G-C, A-U, T-A) etc. respectively (naturally design).. Contrary wise reverse transcription in viruses is that most viruses use reverse transcription to their survival (i.e. the concept of survival of the fittest). For this reason, whether viruses are big or small, if at least they are and so long their

requirement for growth and multiplication is attended with immediate alacrity. Viruses like those of HIV, EBOLA, COVID-19 etc. respectively have an RNA genome and thereby could be converted from RNA to DNA before hijacking the host cell (Silas et al., 2020). There are several viruses that use reverse transcriptase such as human T-lymphotropic virus (HTLV) type 1 and 2 and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). HTLV 1 may cause leukemia, cancer of the white cells in some infected patients by mutating the white blood cell DNA. HTLV 2 has been associated with brain disorder (neurodegeneration) where parts of the brains and spinal cord break down. In like manner HIV is the most well-known e.g. retrovirus when HIV or any other viruses infects a cell it brings with its genome made of RNA single strand and the DNA double strand. The RNA enters the cell and the reverse transcriptase copies the viral RNA to DNA the viral DNA is cut and paste into the host cell DNA. There is always a lot of tricked by the virus (altered the sequence) through which the host cells are being misled for the replication of viruses and this has always become a big set back to human cells as shown in fig 4. The bases for the protein syntheses by the host cells have been altered by the pathogen (virus). The host cells might not necessarily notice and the pathogens would rather be kept on producing replicates of new viruses proteins (not protein synthesis this time around) in localize form that would later be given birth to generalize fashion (spread all over the tissue, kidney, liver, heart etc. respectively Satanic design through arbitrarily or illegal sex harassment.

Figure 3 Posted protein syntheses

Figure 4 Posted divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup at the verge harvesting at primary (young stage) and secondary (older stage) metabolite stage (Enzymology). The process of aerobic fermentation phase I. once again as a microbiologist I always battle with the microorganisms under aseptic condition for standardization. Thus people would not have been ingesting truck load or 'vehicle of pathogens into their respective system for the better

1.4. Artificial vaccine/drugs and human immune system

Breaking New. What is Artificial Vaccine a vaccine is a consisting mainly of synthetic, peptide, carbohydrate or antigen. Most existing vaccine are prepared from inactivated disease causing organism or a suitable part of it e.g. a toxin. However often the antigen to which the immune system responds is relatively small number either acids or peptides. So far so good when there is an out break of a disease or pandemic within a particular region, there is always artificial vaccine or temperamental medication available to humanity so as to curtail the spread of the disease sporadically to the detriment of mankind's. Thus the inferior artificial vaccine produce by various companies as (gambler enterprises) to humans have added more problem to mankind's(aging) as seen in **figure 2(blood clogging)**. Right from the sense or as we've rightly and early have known artificial vaccine / human immune system have always been known synergistically for the role they've been playing against pathogens. For this reason, the synergy relationship played between artificial vaccine and human immune system is only to have kept one status (Healthwise) for a very stipulated schedule frame time (Off and On syndrome). Continue intake of artificial vaccine which has been known to be so inferior to accommodate the pathogen for several years(HIV) and few months for Covid-19 has nothing to write home about. Lo and behold many people who are carriers of viral infections have assiduously and painstakingly become slave or servitude to hospitals or private clinic without letting anyone to have known. It's for our own information to bring to our knowledge of the fact that, in a situation where the pathogen became so acclimatized with artificial vaccine due to its inferiority complex ; then the attenuation of the natural human immune system in-situ would have had emerge. Thus, the pathogen through which the variant develop would rather be comfortably; and gradually modifying its self into another terrible dimension within the human organs, systems, tissues (organelles) for more destruction or as weapon of mass destruction. For this reason, the following persistent illnesses observe from people who are carrier of virial infection under preclinical management are as follows; pile, ulcer, stroke, high blood pressure, arthritis, asthma, cardiovascular disease, liver disease, kidney disease etc., respectively. Nowadays and hospitals or clinics have become more of a consult to perpetual viral infection carrier as servitude or slavery. Surprise singly, one at 20 years is having high blood pressure, at 40 year many could hardly read with their naked eyes due to the fact that the cells have gone damage, at 30 -45 grey hairs and sometime one would start experiencing face wrinkling, partial stroke etc., respectively as results of persistent virial infection due to suppressive HIV/Covid -19 vaccine

Figure 5 Posted reverse transcription in both eukaryotic and prokaryotic cells as the sequence is altered

1.5. Rational / justification of the research

In view of the previous investigation with reference to early aging, aging refers to the universal, progressive, and deleterious changes in organisms that occur with time and which intensifies the probability of several diseases and sometimes leads to death [12]. Interestingly, chronic diseases and aging both are highly linked with DNA mutations, low-grade inflammation, and increased metabolic and oxidative stress, including escalated levels of its damage [13]. The human body is in a continuous fight to stay itself away from aging. One of the well-studied and most prominent theories about aging is the free radical theory of aging [14]. On the contrary, and for the avoidance of one being a clinical test recipe or sample by medical personal (managerial patient using inferior artificial antiretroviral therapy/ inferior artificial covid-19 on a daily, monthly and yearly routine); (it is well when it is not well with the patient) so far the interaction between the pathogen and the immune system/ the vaccine through which the pathogen is in charge of the

pathological processes. Thus, the pathogen detects for the antibodies / vaccine /antiretroviral therapy base on the inferior artificial vaccine/drug. In other word when the pathogen outweigh the strength of the artificial drugs/ antibody then they would have no choice to succumb for the pathogen. lo and be hold the pathogen would rather be strictly, repeatedly and signally gave a sound warning to the antibodies / vaccine /antiretroviral therapy not to chew more than what is expected; otherwise, it would release its worst virulence through sudden variant/change (modification) for total destruction of the host, antibody and the artificial inferior vaccine/drugs to perpetual negativism. On the safer side let maintain the orderliness of synergy relationship for clinical management due to present of the inferior artificial drugs/ covid-19/ antiretroviral therapy of the patient pending when it would have ravaged the patient to early grave under the clinical management. If one may ask how dirty are one’s blood vessel; and is one at the risk of early death? As a matter of truth if ones does not cleared his blood vessel at over 50years, then ones vessel is already gone dirty. Thus, one needs to clean it’s for his/her betterment of life. Let it be known to us cleansing of blood vessel through other means would rather prolong the life of the elderly and stabilize their blood pressure as shown in table 2, plate6, fig 5. In other word may those who are currently force to take pills on a daily bases so as to stabilize their blood pressure no longer need to do so. All one needs to do is to clean one blood vessels even if the hypertension does not go away entirely for “half bread is better than none”. One would rather still feel a lot better (temporarily). Unfortunate corrupt doctors and pharmaceutical companies which benefit from people undergoing a very large routine and expensive treatment are actively trying to keep this drugs so secretive. After all the longer a person remain ill, the more they would have spent on the medicine(clinical Management by the medical personals). Oh...Kush.... Its insanely profitable. Furtherance all these processes are crude and rudimental clinical way of managing the patient through which he/she has sign his/her death warrant. Appropriate cleansing of blood vessels using the divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup is quite simple, inexpensive and affordable for one to get back on their feet with simple technology. However, it does not involved spending a lot of money in the processed of ad mistering the efficacy of the divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup as seen in table 2. My beloved why don’t we give a trial or our ignorance using divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup for permanent cure of many illnesses as shown in table 9&10. Thus, its contain or loaded with all the necessary measures for keeping the longevity of ones age over 100years. The herbal medi-cane is highly fortified with 54 variables gotten from fruits, seeds and leaves with an appreciable amount of measurement. The prove for the clinical trials have been tried on so many people and is found very effective to whosoever that ingest it as a supplement. Thus, newly modified poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup is source of a welcome development produce in Directorate of Research and Development Kad poly. The divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup of all kinds maintain the status of vitamins, minerals, bioactive compounds and antioxidant for all odd of illnesses (clearing of clog with in arteries blood vessel). Breaking new: the pathogen alongside with its variant are under the control of the divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup therapy + the antibody (we are fully in charge of the whole process) as observed in Table2.

Figure 6 Posted the role of vitamins in reverse arteries or un clog

Figure 7 Posted reverse clogged and stiff arteries (50%) atherosclerosis over 40years

Aim and objectives of the research

Aim of this research project is to offer a substantial prove regarding dissatisfaction results from orthodox pharmaceuticals, and the belief that divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup therapy might be so effectively used in treatment of some ailments as well as maintaining the status of one's longevity (antiaging). Contrary wise the systematic intake of the conventional therapy has more or less proven to be so ineffective or inadequate scenario in the field of clinical biosafety.

Figure 8 Posted divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup at the verge harvesting at primary(young stage) and secondary(older stage) metabolite stage (Enzymology) phase II. The process is to open for humanity to see before it gone close

1.6. Research questions

Is the validity of mild alkaline divine chocolate Medi-cane syrup therapy being curable for some certain ailments and age longevity (anti-aging)?

- To what extent to treatment that external life span in animal models slow aging
- Which is a better defining characteristic of antiaging treatment that they inhibits the central process of aging or that they prevent age related disease
- Does the efficacy of divine poly herbal chacolte Medi-cane syrup therapy dosage guarantee the safety of some certain ailments and age longevity (anti-aging)?

1.7. Significance of the study

The use of herbal medicinal products and supplements has increased tremendously over the past three decades with not less than 80% of people worldwide relying on them for some part of primary healthcare. Although therapies involving these agents have shown promising potential with the efficacy of a good number of herbal products clearly established, many of them remain untested and their use are either poorly monitored or not even monitored at all. The consequence of this is an inadequate knowledge of their mode of action, potential adverse reactions, contraindications, and interactions with existing orthodox pharmaceuticals and functional foods to promote both safe and rational use of these agents. Since safety continues to be a major issue with the use of herbal remedies, it becomes imperative, therefore, that relevant regulatory authorities put in place appropriate measures to protect public health by ensuring that all herbal medicines are safe and of suitable quality. In view of the current investigation the divine herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup therapy discussion is limited to toxicity-related issues and major safety concerns arising from the use of herbal medicinal products or medicine as well as factors promoting them. Some important challenges associated with effective monitoring of safety of these herbal remedies with a view to helping refocus relevant regulatory agencies on the need for effectiveness and ensuring adequate protection of public health and promoting safety.

2. Literature review and update (purification/biosafy of chocolate medicane syrup)

2.1. Influence of regulatory policies on safety of herbal medicine

It has been observed that most of the problems associated with the use of traditional and herbal medicines arise mainly from the classification of many of these products as foods or dietary supplements in some countries. As such, evidence of quality, efficacy, and safety of these herbal medicines is not required before marketing. In the same vein, quality tests and production standards tend to be less rigorous or controlled and in some cases, traditional health practitioners may not be certified or licensed. The safety of traditional and herbal medicines has therefore become a major concern to both national health authorities and the general public[15].

Until 2011, there were three possible regulatory routes by which an herbal product could reach a consumer in the UK. The unlicensed herbal remedy is the commonest route which does not have to meet specific standards of safety and quality neither is it required to be accompanied by safety information for the consumer as shown in plate 5 [16]. Recently, the European Union (EU) implemented a directive after a 7-year transition period to harmonize the regulation of traditional herbal medicine products across the EU and establish a simplified licensing system in order to help the public make informed choices about the use of herbal products. This requires that all manufactured herbal products either gain a product license of the type needed to manufacture “conventional” products or become registered as a “traditional herbal medicinal product”[17].

Table 1 Formulation of some selected plants leaves/seeds/fruits variables that makes divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup so perculier

Plants names	Plant extracts	Dose (Concentration)(%)	Approximate concentration of plants extracts syrup 40ml
Sugarcane(<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>)	Shaft Juicer	20	30
Zinger(<i>Zinger officinale</i>)	Rhizome	20	30
Turmeric (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	Rhizome	20	20
Gallic (<i>Allium sativum</i>)	Tiny bulbs Like structures	10	10
Moringa(<i>Moringa oleifera</i>)	Leave/seed	10	30

Testing the entire divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup(Treatment)	Rhizome, leave/seed/ fruit	100	40
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2.2. Toxicity and adverse health effects of some common herbal medicines

In most countries, herbal medicines and related products are introduced into the market without any mandatory safety or toxicological evaluation. Many of these countries also lack effective machinery to regulate manufacturing practices and quality standards. These herbal products are continuously made available to consumers without prescription in most cases and the potential hazards in an inferior product are hardly recognized. It is important to reiterate the staggering rate at which interest and use of herbal medicines is expanding. Over the past decade, the use of herbal medicines represents approximately 40% of all healthcare services delivered in China while the percentage of the population which has used herbal medicines at least once in Australia, Canada, USA, Belgium, and France is estimated at 48%, 70%, 42%, 38%, and 75%, respectively; [18]. In spite of the positive perception of patients on the use of herbal medicines and alleged satisfaction with therapeutic outcomes coupled with their disappointment with conventional allopathic or orthodox medicines in terms of effectiveness and/or safety [19], the problem of safety of herbal remedies continues to remain a major issue of concern.

2.3. Aristolochic acids and *aristolochia* species

Following the discovery of the nephrotoxic and carcinogenic potentials of aristolochic acids, several studies confirmed their genotoxic activity. [20] demonstrated the presence of aristolochic acids-related DNA adducts in renal tissues of patients. These mutagenic adducts when formed are usually poorly repaired and are capable of persisting for years in DNA. Aristolochic acids I and II have been identified in different Asian medicinal plants and also reported to be present in slimming products. This has led to the banning of medicinal products containing these acids in Belgium, UK, Canada, Australia, and Germany.[21]

Figure 9 Posted home base culture medium with mixed culture *Bacillus* and *pseudomonas* species for further distinguish them into pure isolates in response to drugs discovery

Misidentification of medicinal plants and mislabeling herbal medicinal products are sometimes responsible for some of the observed adverse events or interaction and that is the reason it is important to assess herbal medicines for possible presence of adulterants. In the UK and many other countries *Aristolochia fangchi* was linked to the development of subacute interstitial fibrosis of the kidney referred to as “Chinese herbs nephropathy” [22]. Also, recently a 75-year-old man was reported to have died in Australia from kidney failure associated with a toxic preparation containing the root of *Aristolochia fangchi* which he purchased over the internet for psoriasis [23]. This case report suggested the chronic use of aristolochic acid-containing herbal product as the most likely cause of the patient’s death. Similar cases had previously been reported in Taiwan and Japan [24]. Consumption of aristolochic acid-containing Chinese herbal products has also been demonstrated in several studies to be associated with increased risk of urothelial cancer; [25]. A few years back, poisoning that was attributed to Fang-Ji (*Stephania tetrandra* S. Moore) in a weight-loss preparation was actually caused by Guang-Fang-Ji [26].

Table 2 The use of microbial enzyme by product secondary metabolites as antioxidant for antiaging supplements as well as multipurpose therapeutic clinicals

Plant leaves/fruits/ seed/scientific names	Potentials phytochemical virus/bacteria tregetous	nitrogen	Biochemical synthesis	Vitamins	Minerals	Recommended therapeutic efficiency
Zinger (Zinger officinale)	Saponin, tannin, Oxalates, Flavonoid Glycoside Phytates Steroid Alkaloid Sesquiterpenes hydroxy anthraquinone	N	Phenolic compounds(gingerol, Shogaols, parasols) terpene, Organic acid	A, B1 B2, B3, C, D E	Fe, Ca, K Na, Mn, Cu, Fe, Se, P	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medi-cane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti- inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments
Turmeric (Curcuma longa)	Saponin, tannin, Oxalates, Flavonoid Glycoside Phytates Steroid Alkaloid Sesquiterpenes hydroxy anthraquinone	N	Curcumin, desmethoxycurcumin Bisdemethoxycurcumin	A, B1 B2, B3, C, D E	Fe, Ca, K Na, Mn, Cu, P S Cu Se Fe	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medi-cane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti- inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments
Garlic(<i>Allium sativum</i>)	Alkaloid, terpenoid, Anthraquinone Flavonoid	Nitrogen	Ajoene, allicin, allyl,		Calcium (Ca), Iron (Fe) Potassium (K) mangansa(Mn)	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medi-cane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti- inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments
Cauliflower(Brassica oleracea)	Flavonoid, Saponin, Glucosinolates, organosulfur compounds, Monoterpenes, Sesquiterpenes,	N	Carotenoids	A, B6, D, K, C	K, Ca, P, Fe, Zn, Na, Mg	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medicane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti-inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments

	Capsaicinoids& Capsinoids					
Lime fruit /lemon fruit(<i>Citrus aurantitolia/ Citrus lemon</i>)	Flavonoid, Iso-flavonoid, Anthocyanidin, Phytoestrogen, Terpenoids, Polyphenol, Alkaloid	N	Quercetin, Carotene, Rutin, Kaempferol	C, B6, Thiamine, Niacin, Rabo-flavin, B1 B2	Ca, Fe, K P, K,	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medicane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti-inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments
Moringer(<i>Moringer Oleifera</i>)	Saponin, tannin, Oxalates, Flavonoid Glycoside Quinine, Anthraquinone Phenolic compound Terpene Coumarin Steroid Alkaloid Sesquiterpenes hydroxy anthraquinone	N	Carotenoid, Glucosinote Isothiocyanate	A(Beta carotene) B1(Thiamine) B2(Riboflavin) B3(Niacin) B6(Phyrodixine) B7(Biotin) C(Ascorbic acid),K D(cholecalciferol) E(Tocopherol)	Fe, Ca, K Na, Mn, Cu, P S Cu Se Fe	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medicane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti-inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments
Sugarcane (<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>)	Phytosterol, terpenoid, flavonoid, glycosides, phenolic acid, tannin, tetraterpenes	Nitrogen	Carotenoid, luteolin-8-(rhamnosy/ glucoside)	C, B1, B2, B6	Fe, Ca, mg, K, Na, zn, Cu,S	Part of the major prerequisite of polyherbal medicane syrup Therapy which has been solely known to have anti aging & Anti-inflammatory properties to so many patients or peoples as well as other Ailments

The presence of aristolochic acids in the latter produced dramatic adverse reactions which led to nephrotoxic and carcinogenic events in more than 100 women using this weight-loss preparation [27]. In this instance, the similarity in the names of the two herbal products was responsible for the confusion and the unfortunate events.

2.4. *Ephedra sinica*

Ephedra is a very popular herb with long history of traditional use in respiratory conditions [28]. This herb, whose efficacy has been demonstrated in a number of randomized double-blind clinical trials (Boozer et al., 2002) [28], is currently included in the Chinese Pharmacopoeia for therapeutic use and classified as non-toxic. It is an ingredient in commonly used formulary preparations such as Xiaoqinglong Heji for common cold and Zhisou Dingchuan Koufuye for asthma [29]. *Ephedra* has been marketed in the US as a weight-loss dietary supplement and its use associated with a number of serious cardiovascular and central nervous systems (CNSs) adverse effects [30]. Several case reports have also linked the use of *Ephedra sinica* and *Ephedra*-containing dietary supplements to adverse events such as hepatotoxicity neurotoxicity and transient blindness. [31],

2.5. *Aconitum* species

Aconitum carmichaeli and *Aconitum kusnezoffii* are used traditionally for pain relief. The toxicity of the medicinal plants derives primarily from the presence of diester diterpene alkaloids such as aconitine, mesaconitine, and hyaconitine in them [32]. These medicinal plants constitute important ingredients in some commonly used herbal preparations like Sini Tang, Fuzi Lizhong Wan, and Guifu Dihuang Wan for stroke and heart failure, diarrhea and diabetes, respectively [33]. Poisoning due to homemade medicated liquor containing aconite and traditional medicine containing A

2.6. GARLIC (*Allium sativum*)

Garlic has found relevance for management of hypertension and hypercholesterolemia besides its use as a food or food additive. It is known to contain alliin, which on crushing or chopping in the absence of heat or acid becomes activated by alliinase to allicin. Adverse effects associated with garlic extract including burning sensation in the gastrointestinal tract, nausea, diaphoresis, and lightheadedness have been reported. This extract may also cause contact dermatitis and morbid spontaneous spinal epidural hematoma has been attributed solely to excess garlic ingestion [34].

2.7. *Ginkgo biloba* and ginseng

Ginkgo biloba has found widespread use in a variety of conditions and several products such as elixirs, extracts, tea, as well as capsules and tablets that may differ in terms of content, have been made from the dried root). The whole root which contains ginsenosides is usually used because these compounds possess specific pharmacologic effects that may oppose each other [35]. Over 30 ginsenosides have been identified and these compounds are being investigated for their ability to inhibit cell proliferation, tumor cell invasion, and/or metastasis. Recently, the ability of ginsenosides to modulate signaling pathways involving cell cycle, inflammatory, or growth factor pathways, was demonstrated [36]. The leaf extracts of ginkgo had also been demonstrated to contain active compounds that had found usefulness in improving circulation and cognition [37]. The plant extracts appear to be relatively safe, although headache, dizziness, restlessness, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and dermal sensitivity are the most common side effects that have been observed. *Ginkgo* has been demonstrated to be capable of inhibiting platelet-activating factor and altering bleeding times. Therefore, cautious use had been advised in individuals or patients on anticoagulants therapy. The ability of ginkgo to induce liver cancer in experimental model was reported recently and genotoxic mechanisms were suggested to play some role in the carcinogenic process [38].

2.8. Challenges associated with monitoring safety of herbal medicine

With the enormous global consumption of herbal products and medicines, it is high time they were included in pharmacovigilance systems. In terms of population exposure alone, it is essential to identify the risks associated with the use of herbal medicines, and in this regard, the safety of these products has become an issue of great public health importance [39]. There is no doubt that the increasing cases of poisoning associated with the use herbal medicines in many parts of the world in recent times, is necessitating the need to ensure thorough toxicity assessment alongside active pharmacovigilance on these products in order to promote their safe use and protect public health [40]

2.9. Challeges associated with monitoring safty of herbal medicines

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many parts of the world in recent times, is necessitating the need to ensure thorough toxicity assessment alongside active pharmacovigilance on these products in order to promote their safe use and protect public health [42].

The development as well as implementation of the regulation of traditional or herbal medicines in different parts of the world is often confronted with several challenges. Challenges often encountered and common to many countries are those related to regulatory status, assessment of safety and efficacy, quality control, safety monitoring and inadequate or poor knowledge about traditional, complementary/alternative, and herbal medicines within national drug regulatory authorities [43].

Table 3 Types of antioxidants

Endogenous antioxidant s	Exogenous antioxidants
Enzymatic	Mineral elements
Catalase	Selenium
Superoxide dismutase	Zinc
Glutathione	Manganese
Glutamyl trans peptidase	Copper
Non enzymatic	Nutritional
Uric acid	Carotenoid
Ubiquinone	Vitamin C
Tocopherol	Vitamin E
Retinol	Phytochemical
Glutathione	Supplementation
Melatonin	B-carotene, Coenzyme, lipoic acid, polyphenol, Glutathione, Phytoestrogens

Figure 10 Posted the process divine polyherbal chocolate medicine aliquot not yet syrup. Undergoing basification to neutralization point using home base processed KOH, NaOH, CaOH, etc respectively

2.10. Challenges related to the regulatory status of herbal medicines

The definition and categorization of herbal medicines vary from one country to another. Depending on the regulations applying to foods and medicines, a single medicinal plant may be categorized as a food, a functional food, a dietary supplement, or a herbal medicine in different countries. This introduces serious difficulty in the definition of the concept of herbal medicines for the purposes of national drug regulation while at the same time also confusing patients and consumers [44]. In the United States, for example, natural products are regulated under the Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act (DSHEA) of 1994 [45]. By definition, a dietary supplement is a product that is ingested and is intended to supplement the diet and contains a “dietary ingredient.” The dietary ingredients in these products may include vitamins, minerals, herbs, or other botanicals as shown in table 2 and plate 6 [46]. Under the DSHEA, additional toxicity studies are generally not required if the herb has been on the market prior to [47]. In this regard, the FDA bears the burden to prove that an herbal medicinal product or “dietary ingredient” is toxic or not safe for use. Additional major challenge in many countries is the fact that regulatory information on herbal medicines is often not shared between regulatory authorities and safety monitoring or pharmacovigilance centers [48].

2.11. Challenges related to the assessment of safety and efficacy

There is no gainsaying the fact that the requirements as well as the research protocols, standards and methods needed for the evaluation of the safety and efficacy of herbal medicines are much more complex than those required for conventional or orthodox pharmaceuticals [49]. A single herbal medicine or medicinal plant may contain hundreds of natural constituents, and a mixed herbal medicinal product may contain several times that number. Suppose every active ingredient were to be isolated from individual herb from which the herbal medicine is formulated or produced, the time and resources required would be tremendous. Such an analysis may practically be impossible especially where an herbal product is a mixture of two or more herbs [50].

2.12. Challenges related to quality control of herbal medicines

The quality of the source materials used in the production of herbal medicines determines to a large extent the safety and efficacy of these herbal remedies. Generally, the quality of source materials is dependent not only on intrinsic (genetic) factors, but also on extrinsic factors like environmental conditions, good agricultural, and good collection practices (GACP) for medicinal plants, including plant selection and cultivation. It is the combination of these factors that makes it difficult to perform quality controls on the raw materials of herbal medicines (WHO, [51]). According to good manufacturing practice (GMP), correct identification of species of medicinal plants, special storage, and special sanitation and cleaning methods for various materials are important requirements for quality control of starting materials

3. Methodology

The method employed was primarily based on the literature review approach, alongside with current plates employ for the success of project work. Thus, which was quantitatively and qualitatively featured by nature’s called (phytochemical, bioactive compounds, minerals and vitamins assessing in plants, seeds as well as fruits in-situ. Thus, the processes taken to arrive from the raw to the finishing were guided by scheme emerging potential of antioxidant, supplementation as antiaging agent on delayed aging process, anti-viral properties, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial properties, anti-viral anti fungi, antarthritic etc., respectively. This traditional and medicinal methodology for exploiting locally available endogenous raw material to the finishing under aseptic condition is a welcoming and open door for researchers to explore as many of these plants so as to solving the lingering problem in the community.

3.1. Update complexity of divine poly herbal chocolate medicane syrup and its biosafety healthwise investigational herbs/seeds, fruits and rhizomes formulation of (poly herbal medicane syrup)

Investigational herbs from leaves, Seeds, Rhizome and Fruits like those of waterleaves, bitter leaves, ginger, turmeric sugar cane, mints, tomatoes, cucumber, broccolis, Bell pepper, apples, onion, kale, cauliflower, Avocado fruits, Avogadro seed, Beetroot, Adua, Tamarind, carrot, peas, soya bean, green tea, common bean, lime, banana, cabbage etc respectively are known to have been found in part of Asia and Africa. In west Africa, Nigeria they are abundantly found in Sahel region, savanna, and the tropic. it has been reported that most of the Highlighted nutraceutical anti aging medicane syrup are heavenly rich in alkaloids, coumarin, phenolic compounds, saponins, flavonoid, glycosides triterpenoids, amino acids, carbohydrate, proteins, vitamins, mineral, sterol etc respectively ashown in table 2 (silas et al..... 2021) [52]

Their pharmacological actions reported as antioxidant, antiaging, analgesic, anti-inflammatory and wound healing, anti-allergic, neuroprotective, cytotoxic and anti-tumour, dermatological, anti-hemorrhagic, antiviral(covid-19,HIV,

influenza, papilloma, Ebola etc respectively), hepatoprotective, antidiabetic(type I&II), antipyretic, hematological, [53] free radical scavenging, ferric reducing and iron chelation, antimicrobial, and anti-fungal [54]activities as shown in table 4 &5

The divine poly herbal medicane syrup(multipurpose broad spectrum) is also used in the hepatic, neurological, and hematological problems, dysentery, fever, thirst, vomiting, gastritis, inflammation, and skin diseases, thalassemia, cardio-protective, iron chelation. urinary disorders, and analgesia, beneficial to treat bronchitis, burns, gastritis, enteritis, neuralgia, headaches, fever, irritable bladder, and prostatic hyperplasia. [55] anticancer, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, and many more[56]. It is used in the treatment of neurological, gastrointestinal, hepato-biliary, endocrinological, hematological, cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, dermatological disorders. [57].

3.2. Types of antioxidants

Oxidant-antioxidant balance is crucially important in maintaining healthy biological systems. Under physiological conditions, the human antioxidative defense system, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), and glutathione (GSH), allows the elimination of excess reactive oxygen species (ROS), including superoxide anions (O_2^-), hydroxyl radicals ($HO\cdot$), and alkoxy radicals ($RO\cdot$). In addition, exogenous compounds with reducing capacity, such as vitamin C, vitamin E, carotenoids, and polyphenols are also essential for intact functioning of endogenous antioxidant defense system. Therefore, there is continuous demand for exogenous antioxidants to prevent oxidative stress as shown in table 1. Having taken simultaneously and experimentally animal studies include epidemiological evidences and human studies in animal studies, long-term in-take of natural foods such as apples, olives, and honey has been shown to cause some adverse effects related to aging, including oxidative stress in the brain, mental disorders, and anxiety. Potential side effects of exogenous antioxidants on healthy humans have been first revealed by demonstrating the carcinogenic and toxic effects of synthetic antioxidants such as butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) and butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) on rodents and apes at high concentrations, possibly with a pro-oxidative effect. Surprisingly, in animal models, BHA has been reported to exhibit anticarcinogenic activity against different carcinogens [58]. These different findings may be explained by the dose administered during treatment. In a certain part of the world, humans take 0.1 mg/kg of BHA and BHT per day. The LD 50 dose of these synthetic exogenous antioxidants has been reported to be 2 mg/kg in several animal studies, and its toxicity on human health has been increasingly confirmed in cases of chronic intake. Interestingly, the presence of antioxidants such as BHT and BHA in foods at high concentrations may also increase their deterioration depending on their pro-oxidant activity, rather than increasing their shelf life (38). Going by the result obtain in table 1, 6 and 7 revealed that apart from the synthetic antioxidant which is prone to have severe adverse effect to humans in reciprocal to divine polyherbal chocolate medicane which is very efficient to one's health wise care. Thus it also have proven that the effective modified antiaging syrup to human's in all ramifications as well as to so many illnesses/one's longevity. Endogenous antioxidants presence through the divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup might also have had an important role, particularly in specific pathological conditions. On the contrary, Exogenous antioxidants properties presence in divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup is to prevent so many ailments either by suppressing oxidative stress-induced DNA damage or otherwise. Antioxidants spotted in our effective chocolate medicane syrup have also been ever known to have necessitating and characterization causal properties between antioxidants, cancer, health disorder, pneumonia, difficulty in breathing, Asthmatic as well as cardiovascular risk shown in table 3, 4 & plate 6

Table 4 Divine polyherbal medicane syrup products

Illness	Symptoms	therapy	Products dosage
Age Spot	Colored patch on the skin(pigmentation due to the insufficient fat production by the by the sebaceous glands under the skin	Anti Age Spot	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days
Aging	Multidimensional process of physical, psychological and social change	Anti aging	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days
AIDS/HIV Positive	Disease that kills the immune system (defense) of the body leaving it (body) open to all kinds of disease characterized by loss of appetite, weight loss constant headaches etc this is deadly	Anti HIV/AIDs	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 7days

Arthritis	Inflammation or pains and swelling in the joints especially knee joints	Anti Arthritis	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days. After three days ones could comfortably take it on his/her leisure time; hence, it is a supplement
Asthma	Disease of the bronchial tubes which lead from the wind pipe or trachea into lungs causing panting, shortness of breath almost suffocating (technically called bronchial asthma	Anti Asthma	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days.. After three days ones could comfortably take it on his/her own leisure time; hence, it is a supplement
Atherosclerosis	Disease of the bronchial tubes which lead substances called cholesterol in the system characterized by hypertension and cholesterol related sickness	Anti Atherosclerosis	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days. After three days ones could comfortably take it on his/her leisure time; hence, it is a supplement
Sinusitis	Inflammation of sinus (the cavity or hollow space particularly those in the bones of the nose especially the maxillary sinus. Characterized by acute catarrh fever chills cough, headaches etc	Anti-Sinusitis	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days.. After three days ones could comfortably take it on his/her own leisure time; hence, it is a supplement
Stomach Ulcer	An open sore in the Stomach	Anti stomach ulcer	Just three tea spoon or the cap daily for 3days.. After three days ones could comfortably take it on his/her own leisure time; hence, it is a supplement

3.3. Ginger (*Zinger officinale*)

This remarkable ingredient not only adds a bust of flavor to dishes but it also offers a range of notable benefits. Ginger abundant in flavonoid, tannin, Glycoside, steroid, anthraquinone, Alkaloid etc., respectively, Bioactive compounds like those of gingerol, shogaols, parodols as well as vitamins and minerals as shown in table 2. This result is in line with the studies made by [59]. On the contrary, taking a critical view of the current investigation s with respect to divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup it involved so many components added to the solution that makes it poly herbal. Thus, if only a single species of ginger could have had made numerous bioactive compounds, antioxidants, minerals as well as vitamins for being antiaging agents; then one could expect so much to be done on divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup. Ginger as a single species which have play a crucial role in protecting the body against harmful free radicals. Moreover, it possesses anti-inflammatory properties that could help alleviate joint pain and reduces inflammation [60]. On the other hands one is expected for polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup to have done a lots through anti-infective actions in all ramifications of the body. It reduces immune function and comorbidities related to aging and increase the risk for developing infection in young and elderly people. In one recent studies which have shown that ginger and its bioactive constituents have antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral activities in particular, ginger and / or its active components were also reported to be active against drug- resistant bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *salmonella typhi*, *staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and *Enterococcus faecalis* and fungi such as *candida albicans* [61] typical example are found in plate 3. In view of the current investigation, the divine herbal poly herbal chocolate medicane syrup does not only base it efficacies on these antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral properties but also on so many ailments as shown in table 4. Furthermore, divine poly herbal chocolate medicane syrup has also been demonstrated to have an outstanding antiviral activity due to a high concentration of antiviral compounds Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an infectious respiratory tract disease caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Since its discovery in 2019, the virus has spread worldwide, causing the COVID-19 pandemic. The disease can be fatal especially in elderly infected patients with comorbidities. Even though there is no definitive treatment or a fully effective vaccine for COVID-19, extensive research is ongoing. But with the current divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup the viral nonstructural protein 15 (Nsp15) is increasingly being considered as an important therapeutic target for the viral replication of SARS-CoV-2. In a recent *in vitro* study using hydroxychloroquine (one of the few artificial drugs recommended for the management of COVID-19) as a positive control or suppressive, it was suggested that gingerol can inhibit viral replication by binding to the Nsp15 viral protein

of SARS-CoV-2 [62]. Additionally, in a very recent publication, it was stated that ginger extract may be used as an adjunctive treatment for COVID-19 due to its demonstrated beneficial effects in acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), pulmonary fibrosis, pneumonia, and sepsis, which also occur in COVID-19 patients [63]. In 2020, Ahkam et al. designed an in silico study to investigate the potential utilization of the antiviral properties of ginger in counteracting SARS-CoV-2 infection based on the interaction of ligand ginger compounds with the viral spike (S) protein and main protease (MPro) [64].

Figure 11 Posted the divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup product in their sterile plastic rubber

Thus, a promising therapeutic strategy would be to develop structure-dependent antiviral drugs based on phytochemical compounds that inhibit essential SARS-CoV-2 proteins base on trying the ignorant of divine poly herbal chocolate medicane syrup for the better.

Figure 12 Posted the divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup on heat treatment

3.4. Garlic (*Allium Sativum*)

Garlic has always been a collagen enrich food and their incredible antiaging benefits. Collagen is the protein responsible for maintain ones skins elasticity and keeping his/her joints flexible as one age. Thus collagen production naturality decline, but fair not because of one could boast it through divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup. In addition divine polyherbal chocolate medicate syrup has been currently explored by many people to achieving their youthful radian skin and promote overall antiaging. Garlic might not be the only first thing that comes to one mind when one thought of antiaging food but it has some remarkable properties which could be beneficial to one skin health. Garlic contains some peculiar antioxidant, bio active component as well as vitamins and mineral supplement that help in keeping one

youthfulness looking so radiant. Thus these compounds are in the form of alkaloid, flavonoid, tannin, anthraquinone saponin etc., respectively. Bio active compounds like those of carotenoid, allicin, alliin, disulfide, ajoene for the maintaining one youthfulness without qualm. Garlic has also been found with abundant of vitamins and minerals supplement like those of A, B1, B2, and Fe, Ca, Mg, Mn, Zn, Se, K etc., respectively as shown in table 2. This study could be adequately in conformation with the previous studies ascribe by [65] Thus the presence of these arrays of antioxidant as well as numerous vitamins and minerals supplement could offered adequately protection against toxic pathogenic free radicals organisms and other ROS. Contrary wise must the argument base on only garlic when it was just a 1/10 of the studies? In view of this current investigation formulated (Divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup) has been known to have numerous fighting force agents in comparison to borak et al 1986 studied. lo and behold the presence of disulfide compound has been known for collaging production. Sulphur is like the scaffolding that help build the collagen frame work in one skins. Further more the divine poly herbal chocolate medicane syrup has been known to have multiple antioxidants such as selenium, and corseting which help combat oxidative stress. Oxidative stress which is cause by free radical/ pathogenic microbial free radical s would rather led to premature aging by damaging the skin cells and accelerating the formation of wrinkle. So an appreciable amount of crude sugar cane extract of garlic was added in the divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup(culinary creation) of the modified solution is not only enhancing the flavor and beauty of the modified syrup but also proactively protecting one skin from effects of oxidative stress. For this reason keeping ones looking so vibrant and youthful as shown in table 2.

3.5. Limefruit/lemon fruit (Citrus aurantifolia/ Citrus/lemon)

Oranges these familiar round fruits are not only sweet/Sour juices but also full of good things for ones body. These citrus fruits are famous for their tasty, flavor and the many ways they could helped to have kept one's health and let learn more about them. Oranges belong to a plant family called Rutaceae and are grown in warm places around the world. One special thing about them is they have a lot of vitamins, bioactive compounds and minerals like those of B1, B2, C, B6, K, Anthocyanidin, Phytoestrogen, Terpenoid, Alkaloid, Polyphenol, Rutin, Kaempferol, Quercetin, Carotene and Mineral like those Ca, Fe, K, P as observe in in table 2. These findings are in line with study ascribe by [66]. According to the study of [67] that there are different types of oranges like Valencia, navel and blood oranges, its types have its own unique tests and qualities. Nutritionally oranges are like a treasure chest of goodness. They have a lot of vitamins which is a very important nutrient that helps makes ones immune system strong. Moreover, oranges are packed with important B vitamins like thiamine and folate. These vitamins are like fuel for one's body-thiamine help give one's energy and folate help one's cell growth property. In addition, all types of oranges have something peculiar in dietary fibers which is like a helper for one's stomach with regards to digestion. It could help lower bad cholesterol, it also keep one's weigh in check and help control one's blood sugar level. If only oranges have all these criterion for checkmating one's body health wise then what about divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup? Wouldn't it be considered as a multi purpose syrup that has all it takes for numerous healing properties spotted in table ? Divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup has special minerals link to potassium, calcium, iron etc., respectively. Thus, the body needs them for one's health and calcium helps one's bone strong. But here's the superhero parts of the syrup which exhibited some powerful health wise care called antioxidant. These special helpers like those of flavonoids and carotenoids fight against oxidative stress in one's body. These stresses could led to problems like heart disease and cancer. One particular carotenoid called beta kryptoxanthin, which is found in the modified syrup might even lower the risk of lung cancers as seen in table 9&10. Often and guest what? Divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup don't just only makes one's inside happy but also are good for ones skin too. Divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup have vehicles of vitamins C which help one's skin stay stretchy and elastic by making a special protein called collagen. Taking Divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup once in a blue moon might likely made one's skin tighter and smoother which means fewer wrinkles and younger looking for babes to be attracted(lover-boy/girl). In addition, the special helper found in Divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup called antioxidant could shield one's skin from harm cause by thing like bad radical and sunlight, this help one's avoid getting old but like (sweet sixteen beauty cream). Numerous Antioxidants in Divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup are like heroes that help one's skin heal on time and a good stopper of inflammations found in table 4. Furtherance the production of vitamin C by industrial fermentation, is based chiefly on Reichstein by this flow chart Reichstein process- Sorbitol---(by fermentation) sorbose- Diacetone sorbose- DAKS – Raw VitaminC- Purified Vitamin C. In this method D- glucose is hydrogenated chemically to produce D- sorbitol. The Bacterial(Actobacter suboxydans) oxidation of D- sorbitol yield L- sorbitol. L- sorbitol is then isolated and condensed acetone to form Diacetone- L- sorbose, The diacetone -L- sorbose is then oxidized to diacetone 2-keto-L- gluconic acids which after hydrolysis, enolization and lactonization yield L- ascorbic acid. The direct oxidation of D- sorbitol or L- sorbose using Acetobacter or Pseudomonas spp has always led to poor yield. A significant yield of sorbose could be obtained by employing a strain of Gluconobacter oxydans ((Ramawat and Shaily Goyal 2009) as shown in plate 3 [68].

Table 5 *In vitro* dpph radical scavenging activity of divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup

Sample	Concentration mg/l	Inhibition %	ICS + SEM Ug
Controls			Average values
SC	0.5	54	60.0
GE	0.5	60	60.6
TM	0.5	64	60.6
GI	0.5	61	60.6
MO	0.5	64	60.6
Treated syrup for drug discovery	0.5	98	113.6

KEY= SC= Sugarcane ; GE= Ginger; TM= turmeric ; GI= garlic ; Mo= Moringa

3.6. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*)

Turmeric nowadays which has been known as golden spice has always been potentially used for human expectancies are increasingly use in traditional medicine. Recent scientific studies have reveal it remarkable and potentials in promoting well -being and combating various health issues. So let uncover the magic of turmeric water crude extract and its extraordinary advantages for individual age 50 and above. Turmeric crude water extract boost immune system as we age and a robust immune system becomes crucial for maintaining good health. Turmeric crude water extract is known to have played a significant role in bolstering one immune defenses. Scientists studies have shown curcumin the bioactive compounds and remarkable rhizome spice that offered a wealth of antioxidant, vitamins and minerals a shown in table. This study agreement with the report of (koral, [69]. On the contrary the current investigations with regards to Koral 2006) studies only turmeric water crude extract was used for the investigation. Furthermore by relating ones investigation with truck load of different appreciable crude water extracts from different plants, seeds, leaves and fruits (antiaging food supplements), this simple technology would have solved the perpetual off and on illnesses for the better on some many people. Divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup have the potentials to combat as many as illnesses as shown in table 2. The divine poly herbal chocolate possesses potent inflammatory and antioxidant properties these properties help enhances the immune response protect against chronic diseases and reduce the risk of infections as shown in table 4 once again. A study published in the journal of clinical immunology demonstrated that curcumin stimulates the activity of immune cells such as killer cell and T cell cells which play a vital role in fighting viral infections like those of HIV/AIDS, Covid-19 and cancer spotted in table 4. Divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup which contains numerous curcumin from different plants, seeds and fruits is the mother of all therapeutic clinical in all ramifications. In view of our current study, it is good for digestive health, maintaining a health digestive system has become increasingly important as we age. The divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup aids digestion by stimulating the production of bile, promoting optimal liver function, improving the breakdown of fats, it also alleviated bloating and reduces the risk of gastrointestinal disorders such as irritable bowel syndrome(IBS). Thus all these are features in. Numerous Curcumin presents in Nigeria divine poly herbal chocolate medi-cane syrup act as inflammatory properties which is known in soothing the intestine lining and reduces inflammation. A study published in the journal of alternative and complementary medicine found that curcumin supplementation improved symptom of (IBS), including abdominal pains and bloating in individual over 50years of age. Nigeria divine polyherbal chocolate medicane syrup helps to prevent Alzheimer's disease as shown in table4. Alzheimer's disease is a significance concern for many individual as they age. The divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup with Even in one stomach most food intake are either weak acid or weak base(base line neutral) and the essence of Dilute HCL in the stomach is to naturized any poisonous substances. So in this process the investigator is trying neutralize any plant extract that found wanting for the best in human system at some certain concentration. Some certain microorganisms which are always rebel in stomach would definitely be neutralized for the best assuredly potent curcumins have shown neuroprotective effects, reducing the accumulation of beta – amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangle, the hallmarks of Alzheimer's. The Nigeria divine polyherbal chocolate medi-cane syrup with abundant curcumins helps reduce cholesterol, level, liver, blood pressure and prevent the further formation of blood clots as seen in plate table 4, plate 6.

Figure 13 Posted the investigator trying basified the weak acid solution by introducing home base process organic alkaline for either neutralization or basification by pH 7-8.

4. Conclusion and recommendation

The global acceptance and use of herbal medicines and related products continue to assume exponential increase. Issues relating to adverse reactions in recent times are also becoming more vivid, increasing in prevalence and no longer debatable because of previous misconception of regarding or categorizing herbal medicinal products as “safe” because they are derived from “natural” source. The reality is that “safety” and “natural” are not synonymous. Therefore, regulatory policies on herbal medicines need to be standardized and strengthened on a global scale. Relevant regulatory authorities in different countries of the world need to be proactive and continue to put in place appropriate measures to protect public health by ensuring that all herbal medicines approved for sale are safe and of suitable quality.

Providers of medicines, such as physicians, nurses, and pharmacists, often have little training in and understanding of how herbal medicines affect the health of their patients. Many of them are also poorly informed about these products and how they are being used. Adequate training is now very essential since most patients are almost often on other types of prescription or non-prescription medicines. In spite of the fact that the active involvement of orthodox healthcare professionals is continuously solicited and huge responsibility lies with them in terms of their valuable contributions to safety monitoring of medicinal products, it is also very important that all providers of herbal medicines are sufficiently empowered to play a role in monitoring safety of herbal medicines. This, however, should be in collaboration with the orthodox healthcare professionals. For this to be effective, it would be essential to create an atmosphere of trust to facilitate adequate sharing of knowledge about the use and safety of herbal medicines. In fact, the education of healthcare professionals, providers of herbal medicines, and patients/consumers is vital for the prevention of potentially serious risks from misuse of herbal medicines.

Of crucial importance also is an appropriate knowledge base relevant to diagnostic and treatment decision-making. Furthermore, individual healthcare provider should also show sufficient commitment toward understanding the use of herbal medicines. This can be by asking relevant questions about the use of these herbal remedies among others whenever they encounter patients who are taking these medications. Health professionals who work in poisons centers and health information services also need to be informed about herbal medicines. Finally, as with other medicines for human use, it has become mandatory that herbal medicines are covered in every country of the world by a drug regulatory framework to ensure that they conform with required standards of safety, quality, and efficacy.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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